

Type of manuscript: Research Article**BIO-POTENTIAL OF A GREEN MARINE ALGAE *Chaetomorpha antennina* (Bory de Saint-Vincent) Kützing) ON THE LIFE CYCLE OF A POLYPHAGOUS INSECT *Spodoptera litura* (Fabricius)*****V.DEVANATHAN and S. BALAMURUGAN**Assistant Professor, Department of Botany, Periyar Arts College, Cuddalore., 607001.,
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Abstract

Chaetomorpha antennina (Bory de Saint-Vincent) Kützing, a green marine alga collected from the Puducherry coast, India, was investigated for its biological activity against the polyphagous pest *Spodoptera litura* Fabricius. Acetone, methanol, and chloroform extracts of *C. antennina* at concentrations of 1, 3, 10, 30, 50, 70, and 100 µl/ml were tested against homogeneous third-instar larvae of *S. litura* under a completely randomized design. The effects were compared with solvent control and untreated control. Treated larvae were observed for larval mortality, pupal mortality, adult emergence, and repellent and antifeedant activities, and the data were recorded systematically. The larvicidal activity of acetone, methanol, and chloroform extracts of *C. antennina* showed no significant effect up to 24 h of treatment. Among the treatments, the acetone extract exhibited the highest larval mortality (66.67%), followed by methanol and chloroform extracts. Although larval mortality increased gradually across treatments, pupation varied significantly, and pupal-to-adult conversion was comparatively lower in all treatments. Adult emergence data revealed that the solvent effect of *C. antennina* (10%) resulted in pupal-to-adult conversion ratios of 1:0.54, 1:0.40, and 1:0.50 for acetone, methanol, and chloroform extracts, respectively, whereas the control and solvent control recorded a higher ratio of 1:0.92.

Keywords: *Chaetomorpha antennina*; solvent extracts; *Spodoptera litura*; bio-potential**Introduction**

Marine algae are widely distributed throughout the intertidal and subtidal regions of marine ecosystems and comprise approximately 844 species belonging to 271 genera²⁴. These marine resources have been reported to possess diverse biological activities, including bactericidal^{7,14}, fungicidal^{4,21}, and insecticidal properties^{9,23}. *Chaetomorpha antennina* (Bory de Saint-Vincent) Kützing is a green marine alga characterized by unbranched filaments forming a clump-like

thallus. Molecular phylogenetic studies have shown that this taxon belongs to a paraphyletic assemblage closely related to branched *Cladophora* species¹¹. The tobacco cutworm, *Spodoptera litura* Fabricius, is a highly destructive polyphagous pest reported to infest more than 112 plant species belonging to 44 families, causing severe economic losses in agricultural systems²⁵. The indiscriminate and prolonged use of chemical insecticides over the past three decades has resulted in several adverse consequences, including insect resistance, pest resurgence, pesticide residues, health hazards, environmental pollution, global warming, and greenhouse effects. In view of mitigating these detrimental impacts, scientists and researchers have been urged to explore eco-friendly and sustainable alternatives to synthetic pesticides²⁶. Among the various alternatives, marine algae have emerged as a promising resource for future pest management research owing to their rich reservoir of bioactive compounds¹⁰. In this context, the present study was undertaken to evaluate the biological efficacy of solvent extracts of *C. antennina* against the polyphagous pest *S. litura*.

Materials and Methods

Collection and Preparation of Seaweed

The green marine alga *Chaetomorpha antennina* (Chlorophyta) was collected from the intertidal and inundated bedrock regions of Puducherry beach, India. The collected algal samples were immediately washed with fresh seawater and subsequently rinsed thoroughly three times with tap water to remove adhering salts, sand particles, and epiphytes. The cleaned algal material was shade-dried at room temperature as described² and stored at 4 °C until further use.

Mass Rearing of Test Insect

The test insect, *Spodoptera litura* Fabricius, was mass reared under laboratory conditions. Larvae were maintained on their natural diet of fresh castor (*Ricinus communis*) leaves in sterilized plastic containers. The culture was maintained following standard rearing procedures, and the required larval stage was obtained from the laboratory culture as described¹⁷.

Preparation of Seaweed Solvent Extracts

Partially powdered seaweed of *Chaetomorpha antennina* (30 g), divided into three portions of 10 g each, was subjected to solvent extraction using a Soxhlet apparatus. Each portion was refluxed separately with solvents of increasing polarity, namely chloroform, acetone, and methanol, for 12 h continuously until the solvent extract became clear. The solvent extracts were concentrated by evaporation and dried under vacuum in a desiccator. The dried crude extracts were re-dissolved in their respective solvents, stored at –20 °C, and used for subsequent bioassay experiments.

Bioassay Procedure

The prepared solvent extracts of *C. antennina* (acetone, methanol, and chloroform) were tested at concentrations of 3, 10, 30, 50, 70, and 100 µl/ml against uniformly aged third instar larvae of *Spodoptera litura* using the leaf-dip method. Corresponding solvent controls and an untreated control were maintained for comparison.

Fresh castor (*Ricinus communis*) leaf discs (5 cm diameter) were dipped in the respective treatment solutions for 10 min, shade-dried, and placed in sterile Petri plates. Five treated leaf discs were placed in each Petri plate, and four-hour-starved third instar larvae (homogeneous population) were introduced. Each treatment was replicated three times with five larvae per replication under a completely randomized design.

Larvae were allowed to feed on the treated leaves, and observations on larval mortality, pupation, and adult emergence were recorded at regular intervals following the method¹⁷. Observations on malformation of pupae and adults were also recorded, documented, and statistically analyzed as per Gomez and Gomez (1984).

Results and Discussion

Investigations on the insecticidal activity of *Chaetomorpha antennina* solvent extracts revealed no observable effect up to 24 h after treatment. During subsequent observation periods (1–6 days), larval mortality generally increased; however, inconsistent mortality patterns were observed during certain intervals. An increasing trend in larval mortality was recorded on the 1st, 3rd, 5th, and 6th days of treatment compared to the preceding day, whereas a reduced level of mortality was observed on the 2nd and 4th days.

Mortality data recorded on the 7th day indicated that the maximum larval mortality occurred at the highest concentration (100 µl/ml) of *C. antennina* solvent extracts, with mortality rates of 73.33%, 60.00%, and 53.33% for acetone, methanol, and chloroform extracts, respectively. This was followed by the next lower concentration, which recorded mortality values of 53.33%, 46.67%, and 40.00%, respectively. In contrast, solvent control (T8) treatments showed mortality levels of 26.67%, 26.67%, and 13.33%, while untreated control larvae exhibited only 13.33% mortality across all experiments (Table 1).

Comparison among the three solvents clearly demonstrated that acetone extract exerted a higher larvicidal effect than methanol and chloroform extracts. These findings are consistent with earlier studies² who reported that methanol extracts of *Ulva fasciata* and *U. lactuca* caused the highest nymphal mortality in *Dysdercus cingulatus*. The same study also documented reductions in relative growth rate, adult longevity, fecundity, and hatchability of the test insect.

The experiment was continued until adult emergence in both treated and untreated insects. The influence of seaweed extracts on pupation exhibited considerable variation among treatments. Significant differences in pupation were observed between treatments and controls. The lowest pupation was recorded at 100 µl/ml concentration (T7) in all three solvent extracts, with pupation percentages of 26.67%, 46.67%, and 33.33% for acetone, methanol, and chloroform extracts, respectively. In contrast, maximum pupation (86.67%) was observed in the control.

Among the lowest concentration treatments (1 µl/ml), chloroform extract showed reduced pupation (60.00%) compared to acetone (73.33%) and methanol (80.00%) extracts. However, at the highest concentration, acetone extract exerted the strongest inhibitory effect on pupation when compared to methanol and chloroform extracts (Fig. 1).

Adult emergence data revealed an inverse relationship between concentration and emergence rate. At 100 µl/ml concentration (T7), adult emergence was limited to 13.33%, 13.33%, and 20.00% in acetone, methanol, and chloroform extract treatments, respectively. In contrast, lower concentrations (1 µl/ml) resulted in comparatively higher adult emergence values of 33.33%, 40.00%, and 40.00%, respectively, although these values remained significantly lower than the corresponding controls.

Among the three solvent extracts, acetone consistently demonstrated superior efficacy in suppressing adult emergence, as none of its tested concentrations allowed more than 50% adult emergence. In contrast, methanol and chloroform extracts permitted more than 50% adult emergence at lower concentrations (Fig. 2).

The pupal-to-adult conversion ratio at 100 µl/ml concentration was recorded as 1:0.50, 1:0.40, and 1:0.42 for acetone, methanol, and chloroform extracts, respectively, which were markedly lower than the control. The lowest pupal-to-adult conversion ratios were observed at 70 µl/ml concentration (T6) for acetone (1:0.28) and chloroform (1:0.33) extracts, whereas methanol extract showed the lowest ratio (1:0.40) at 100 µl/ml (T7). In all solvent extracts, adult emergence differed significantly among treatments and controls, and pupal-to-adult conversion was consistently lower than larval-to-pupal transformation (Table 2).

Similar insecticidal activities of seaweeds have been reported against various insect pests, including *Ascophyllum nodosum* against thrips and mites (Holden and Ross, 2014), *Ulva lactuca* against *Spodoptera littoralis*¹ ;¹⁸ *Colpomenia sinuosa* against stored product pests²⁰, *U. fasciata* against *S. litura*¹⁷, and *Liagora ceranoides* against *S. litura*¹⁶

The insecticidal potential of seaweeds has been attributed to various bioactive compounds such as saponins, phlorotannins, terpenoids, phenols, flavonoids, fatty acids, steroids, and alkaloids reported from different algal species. Similar bioactive constituents may be present in *C. antennina*, which warrants further investigation to identify plant defense chemicals responsible for the observed insect growth regulatory effects.

Table 1

Effect of *Chaetomorpha antennina* solvent extracts on larval mortality of *Spodoptera litura*

Treatments	Meanlarvalmortality%by		
	Acetone extract	Methanol extract	Chloroform extract
T ₁	26.67 ^c (30.78)	26.67 ^d (30.78)	20.00 ^{cd} (22.36)
T ₂	26.67 ^c (30.78)	26.67 ^c (30.78)	26.67 ^{bc} (30.78)
T ₃	33.33 ^c (34.63)	26.67 ^c (30.78)	26.67 ^{bc} (30.78)
T ₄	46.67 ^b (43.07)	40.00 ^b (39.23)	33.33 ^b (34.63)
T ₅	46.67 ^b (43.07)	46.67 ^a (43.07)	40.00 ^a (39.23)
T ₆	53.33 ^a (46.92)	46.67 ^a (43.07)	40.00 ^a (39.23)
T ₇	73.33 ^a (59.21)	60.00 ^a (50.77)	53.33 ^a (46.92)
T ₈	26.67 ^c (30.78)	26.67 ^c (30.78)	13.33 ^{de} (18.13)
T ₉	13.33 ^d (18.13)	13.33 ^d (18.13)	13.33 ^{de} (18.13)
SEd	7.4805	3.9731	4.8712
CD (=0.5)	15.7161	8.3472	9.7845

Each value is an average of three replicates; figures enclosed in parentheses are arc sinetransformed values; means followed by a common alphabet are not significantly different at 5% level by LSD

Table2.Effectof*Chaetomorphaantennina*'ssolventextractsonpupaltoadultconversion

Treatments	Pupalto adult conversion ratio		
	Acetone extract	Methanol extract	Chloroform extract
T ₁	1 : 0.50	1 : 0.75	1 : 0.54
T ₂	1 : 0.36	1 : 0.55	1 : 0.41
T ₃	1 : 0.50	1 : 0.57	1 : 0.54
T ₄	1 : 0.36	1 : 0.50	1 : 0.45
T ₅	1 : 0.36	1 : 0.67	1 : 0.40
T ₆	1 : 0.28	1 : 0.67	1 : 0.33
T ₇	1 : 0.50	1 : 0.40	1 : 0.42
T ₈	1 : 0.54	1 : 0.70	1 : 0.50
T ₉	1 : 0.92	1 : 1.00	1 : 0.92

Fig.2. Effect of solvent extract of *C. antennina* on the adult emergence of *S. litura*

Conclusion

Chaetomorpha antennina exhibited a greater inhibitory influence on adult emergence than on larval and pupal mortality of *Spodoptera litura*. This suppression of adult emergence suggests a possible insect growth regulatory (IGR) activity of the seaweed extracts. Further studies are required to isolate and characterize the bioactive compounds responsible for this effect and to evaluate their potential application in eco-friendly pest management strategies.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

The authors have no conflicts of interest regarding this investigation.

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